

ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL STUDY SKILLS PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN THE CENTRE OF FOUNDATION STUDIES

Leovigildo Lito D. Mallillinⁱ

PhD, Centre of Foundation Studies,
Gulf College, Sultanate of Oman

Abstract:

General Study Skills (GSS) is one of the modules that will equip students in their fundamental studies. It will help them to make use of their time and become effective learners and develop research skills and communicative skills among them. The aim of the study is to assess the performance of the written report output of the respondents in terms of their portfolio, guided learning and group oral presentation and to identify the respondents' performance of their learning outcome in their module along the area of management time and accepting responsibility, research skills, taking notes and giving presentation. The study employed the descriptive correlational designs as this method describes and predicts how two variables are measured which are all about the performance of students in their written report output in their portfolio, guided learning, oral group presentation and in their learning outcome on the management time and accept responsibility, research skills, taking notes, giving presentation from their General Study Skills (GSS) module. The subjects of the study comprised of Nine (9) lecturers of the General Study Skills module. Results show that performance of students in their written report output in terms of portfolio is not met, guided learning is moderately met and group oral presentation is moderately met, however; performance of students in their learning output in terms of management time and accept responsibility is moderately met, research skills is moderately met, note taking is moderately met and giving oral presentation is moderately met.

Keywords: general study skills (GSS), portfolio, guided learning, group presentation

1. Introduction

General Study Skills (GSS) is one of the modules that will equip students in their fundamental studies. It will help them to make use of their time and become effective learners and develop research skills and communicative skills among them. General Study Skills is one of the most widely used construct in educational research and

ⁱ Correspondence: email loviedsunbright_0722@yahoo.com.ph

assessment among the students in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). Students are taught on the different skills not only skills in their General English Language (GEL) but also cover all the skills needed in the module to measure their academic success. This is intended to attain outcome specifically to their learning experiences on their overall assessment as evident on their learning development (York, Gibson & Rankin, 2015).

However, the learning outcome of the General Study Skills demonstrates the ability of the students to manage their time on the deadline of their project or research and the accept responsibility to a certain task needed in the module, develop research skills, note taking and familiar with the different modes of communication skills through participation in individual or group activities and giving presentation as a part of their portfolio. The learning outcome gives emphasis on curriculum or programme in the Centre of the Foundation Studies (CFS). This is true with the General Study Skills (GSS) module. The systematic criteria are set for the students to follow. This examines the capacity and ability of the students. The support given to students on their learning tasks fragmented the nature of their current knowledge. It is evident that improving their learning will be a challenge to their module tutor (Haßler, Major & Hennessy, 2016).

Furthermore, the indicative contents of the module in the General Study Skills (GSS) help the students to succeed in their learning outcome and thereby use them for their future because the module deals on time management and responsibility, research skills, taking notes and giving presentations. Management time and accepting responsibility use a variety of study techniques, create planners and study schedules noting key date and events particularly to those students who are working and at the same time studying, independently access and use of computer labs and internet for language learning, identify preferred study strategies and based on learning styles, organise a feasibility study schedule that accommodate other responsibilities and describe learning experiences, challenges and insights among them. Management time and accepting responsibility continue to improve and change at an intense rate depends on the needs and demands of a certain task in terms of strategies, structures, systems, boundaries and expectations (Kerzner & Kerzner, 2017). Whereas, research skills is one of the indicative contents in the module where the learners are guided on the key ideas to search for information on their project, use the library, computer lab for their research project. They are guided to extract relevant information from the book or article using their strategies, skimming and scanning for their research, cite sources in accordance with academic conventions, assess the reliability, objectivity and authenticity of their research. Students are often encouraged to maximize their engagement with supervised research and minimize teaching obligations. However, the process of teaching students engaged in inquiry provides practice in the application of important research skills. The quality of methodological skills demonstrated in written research. This generates and contributes substantially to the improvement of essential research skills of students (Feldon et. al., 2011). However, taking notes is another indicative content of the module and techniques of students in their learning process to

recall and define main concept, utilise symbols and abbreviations, extract record key information or the gist from the written or spoken source based on their own interpretation of information, support key points with relevant additional details, use notes to create summary and reproduce key information and supporting details from notes in one's own words. Note taking is a technique or skills to grasp the idea of the topic. It involves listening to what someone has. Write all the details of what is being said. Notes takers are the representation of the skeleton structure of speech. Once you have learnt to recognize then quickly consistent in noting them. The notes must be clear if not it is a waste of time (Gillies, 2017). In like manner, giving presentation is one of the indicative contents of General Study Skills (GSS) module where outline and define the main concepts are required among the learners, plan and conduct presentation based on the information from written material, interviews and surveys, speak in a clearly audible and well-paced voice, follow a presentation format, achieve the key aim of informing the audience, make use of audio/visual aids when giving oral presentation, tailor content and language level of the audience, speak from note in front of the audience using index cards, observe time restrictions in the presentation, organise and present information in a logical order at a comprehensible speed and invite constructive feedback and self-evaluate the presentation. Presentation skills are a guide to the most transferable skills and as a part of the critical development of the students. The ability to present a project clearly, cogently and confidently enormously valuable at every stage of student's lives, whatever module they study, helping them succeed in academic works, job interviews, and in their future working lives. The ability to use the body language effectively, to speak as a part of their learning process in gaining students to speak with fluency and confidence improves their presentation skills (Van & Becker, 2016).

The assessment details of the module is composed of group presentation, portfolio and guided learning. The learning and assessment method in the group presentation of the students are the learning outcome of the module or topic of their own choice. In addition, student portfolio is a compilation of academic work and other form of educational evidence assembled for purposes of evaluating students work output, learning progress and academic achievement in determining whether students have met the learning standard or academic requirements to reflect on their academic goals and progress and in creating a lasting archive of academic work output, accomplishments and other documentation. Similarly to their guided learning work output and progress. Assessment practices can deliver timely data about what students understand. Without assessment, teaching is aimed at the middle. They never know which students are ready for stretch and which needs a re-teaching. Assessment details of students are checking their own knowledge and their own work output in the module. It provides feedback to students on the room of improvement in their learning ability (Griffin & Care, 2014).

2. Statement of the Problem

1. What is the performance of the written report output of students in their general study skills in term of their
 - 1.1 portfolio,
 - 1.2 guided learning and
 - 1.3 group oral presentation?
2. Does the performance of the students met the learning outcome of the module along the area of
 - 2.1 management time and accepting responsibility,
 - 2.2 research skills,
 - 2.3 taking notes and
 - 2.4 giving presentation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of students in their written report output and performance of student in their learning output in their general study skills module?

2.1 Hypothesis

HA: There is a significant relationship between the performance of students in their written report output and performance of student in their learning output in their general study skills module.

HO: There is no significant relationship between the performance of students in their written report output and performance of student in their learning output in their general study skills module.

3. Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive correlational designs as this method describes and predicts how two variables are naturally related in the real world. It examines the two variables under study which are all about the performance of students in their written report output on their portfolio, guided learning, oral group presentation and in their learning outcome on the management time and accept responsibility, research skills, taking notes, giving presentation from their General Study Skills module (Jackson, 2014).

3.1 Research Subject

The subjects of the study are the module lectures of General Study Skills. They are officially lecturer of the Center of Foundation Studies handling GFP Semester 2. Nine (9) lecturers are utilised in the study.

3.2 Sampling Technique

The two non-probability sampling techniques namely, Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling are employed in this study. Convenience Sampling and Purposive

Sampling are non-probability sampling techniques that a researcher uses to choose a sample of subjects/units from a population. This is useful because the researcher has limited resources, time and workforce. It can also be used when the research does not aim to generate results that will be used to create generalizations pertaining to the entire population. Therefore, there is a need to use non-probability sampling techniques. The aim of this study is to assess the performance of the students in their written report, oral group presentation and assess their performance in the learning outcome of the General Study Skills module (Etikan, Musa & Alkassim, 2016).

3.3 Research Instrument

For data gathering purposes, the research use the questionnaire based on the module descriptors of the General Study Skills (GSS) using the following scale

1. Performance of students written report in portfolio

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in portfolio written report
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in portfolio written report
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in portfolio written report
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in portfolio written report
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in portfolio written report

2. Performance of students written report in guided learning

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in guided learning written report
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in guided learning written report
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in guided learning written report
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in guided learning written report
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in guided learning written report

3. Performance of students written report in group oral presentation

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in group oral presentation written report
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in group oral presentation written report

2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in group oral presentation written report
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in group oral presentation written report
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in group oral presentation written report

4. Learning outcome of students in management time and accept responsibility

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome

5. Learning outcome of students in research skills

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in research skills learning outcome
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in research skills learning outcome
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in research skills learning outcome
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in research skills learning outcome
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in research skills learning outcome

6. Learning outcome of students in taking notes

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in taking notes learning outcome
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in taking notes learning outcome
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in taking notes learning outcome

1.80-2.79	Not Met	outcome Students have little skills in taking notes learning outcome
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills taking notes learning outcome

7. Learning outcome of students in giving presentation

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Strongly Met	Students have great skills in giving presentation learning outcome
3.40-4.19	Met	Students have adequate skills in giving presentation learning outcome
2.80-3.39	Moderately Met	Students have limited skills in giving presentation learning outcome
1.80-2.79	Not Met	Students have little skills in giving presentation learning outcome
1.00-1.79	Strongly Not met	Students have no skills in giving presentation learning outcome

4. Results

Table 1: Performance of students in their portfolio written report

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Portfolio is based on the skills needed in the module.	0.233	3.22	Moderately Met	1
2. Portfolio given to students is based on their knowledge in learning the skills.	0.157	2.67	Not Met	3.5
3. Evaluates the module quality in their learning process.	0.141	2.56	Not Met	5.5
4. Determines the academic standards and requirements of the module.	0.141	2.56	Not Met	5.5
5. Helps students to reflect on their academic goals and progress.	0.173	2.78	Not Met	2
6. Provides richer, deeper and more accurate picture of the learning process of the students.	0.157	2.67	Not Met	3.5
7. Represents a performance of the students inside the classroom.	0.103	2.33	Not Met	7
Overall Average Weighted Mean		2.68	Not Met	

Table 1 shows the results of the performance of students in their portfolio written report. Portfolio is based on the skills needed in the module (AWM=3.22) moderately met, helps students to reflect on their academic goals and progress (AWM=2.78) not met, portfolio given to students is based on their knowledge in learning the skills and provides richer, deeper, and more accurate picture of the learning process of the

students (AWM=2.67) not met, evaluates the module quality in their learning process and determines the academic standards and requirements of the module (AWM=2.56) not met and represents a performance of the students inside the classroom (AWM=2.33) not met. The overall (AWM=2.68) not met which means that students have little knowledge in their portfolio written report.

Table 2: Performance of students in their guided learning written report

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Give new learning experiences on the part of the students.	0.233	3.22	Moderately Met	1
2. Design to help students learn from their group.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	3
3. Best way for the students to learn and to do something on their module.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	3
4. Give students a chance to experience a wide range of academic freedom and styles.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	5
5. Giving a chance to work in groups, pairs, debates, presentation and tutorials among them.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	3
6. Guided learning is supplemented by their independent study.	0.173	2.78	Not Met	6.5
7. Improve their skills in carrying out specific tasks among them.	0.173	2.78	Not Met	6.5
Overall Average Weighted Mean		3.00	Moderately Met	

Table 2 shows the results of the performance of students in their guided learning written report, give new learning experiences on the part of the students (AWM=3.22) moderately met, design to help students learn from their group, best way for the students to learn and to do something on their module and giving a chance to work in groups, pairs, debates, presentation and tutorials among them (AWM=3.11) moderately met, give students a chance to experience a wide range of academic freedom and styles (AWM=2.89) moderately met, guided learning is supplemented by their independent study and improve their skills in carrying out specific tasks among them (AWM=2.78) not met. The overall (AWM=300) moderately met which shows that students have limited skills in guided learning written report.

Table 3: Performance of students in their group oral presentation written report

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Explore students to develop skills in their academic study skills.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	2.5
2. Develop their potentials in their presentation	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	2.5
3. Help the students to widen their skills in exploring their topic through research.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	2.5
4. Develop their self-esteem in their exposure to speak in their presentation.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	6
5. Apply the principles of their learning experiences	0.173	2.78	Not Met	7

Leovigildo Lito D. Mallillin
ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL STUDY SKILLS PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS
IN THE CENTRE OF FOUNDATION STUDIES

through their presentation.				
6. Follows the guides and procedures in the presentation among their groups.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	5
7. Assess the performance on their skills in their group presentation.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	2.5
Overall Average Weighted Mean		3.02	Moderately Met	

Table 3 shows the results of the performance of the students in their oral group presentation written report, explore students to develop skills in their academic study skills, develop their potentials in their presentation, help the students to widen their skills in exploring their topic through research and assess the performance on their skills in their group presentation (AWM=3.11) moderately met, follows the guides and procedures in the presentation among their groups (AWM=3.00) moderately met, develop their self-esteem in their exposure to speak in their presentation (AWM=2.89) moderately met and apply the principles of their learning experiences through their presentation (AWM=2.78) not met. The overall (AWM=3.02) moderately met which means that students have limited skills in group oral presentation written report.

Table 4: Performance of students in their learning outcome in management time and accept responsibility

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Work in pairs or groups and participate accordingly i.e. take turns, initiate a discussion, interrupt appropriately, express an opinion.	0.277	3.56	Met	1
2. Follow the policies on attendance and punctuality.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	4
3. Work to impose deadlines and homework on time	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	4
4. Show respect for teachers and others and their rights to have a difference of opinion.	0.233	3.22	Moderately Met	2
5. Create term planners and study schedules noting key dates/events.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	7
6. Independently access and use computer labs and the internet for language learning.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	4
7. Identify preferred study strategies based on learning styles and use a variety of study techniques.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	7
8. Organise a feasible study schedule that accommodates other responsibilities.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	7
9. Describe learning experiences, challenges, insights in a daily journal.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	8
10. Organise and maintain a system of recording vocabulary (keep a vocabulary log).	0.157	2.67	Not Met	9
Overall Average Weighted Mean		3.07	Moderately Met	

Table 4 shows the results of the performance of students in their learning outcome in management time and accept responsibility, work in pairs or groups and participate accordingly i.e. take turns, initiate a discussion, interrupt appropriately, express an opinion (AWM=3.56) met, show respect for teachers and others and their rights to have a difference of opinion (AWM=3.22) moderately met, follow the policies on attendance and punctuality, work to impose deadlines and homework on time, and independently access and use computer labs and the internet for language learning (AWM=3.11) moderately met, create term planners and study schedules noting key dates/events, identify preferred study strategies based on learning styles and use a variety of study techniques and organise a feasible study schedule that accommodates other responsibilities (AWM=3.00) moderately met, describe learning experiences, challenges, insights in a daily journal (AWM=2.89) moderately met and organise and maintain a system of recording vocabulary (AWM=2.67) not met. The overall (AWM=3.07) moderately met which means that students have limited skills in management time and accept responsibility learning outcome among them.

Table 5: Performance of students in their learning outcome in research skills

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. List the key ideas to guide search for information.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	3.5
2. Use the library system for finding, borrowing and returning library material.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
3. Use an English dictionary for language learning.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
4. Use a content page and an index to locate information in a book.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
5. Extract relevant information from a book or article using a battery of reading strategies (e.g. skimming, scanning, etc.).	0.173	2.78	Not Met	11
6. Locate a book/journal in the library using the catalogue.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
7. Find topic-related information in a book/journal in the library using the catalogue.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
8. Find specific information using internet search engines and electronic resources.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	1.5
9. Cite a source in accordance with academic conventions.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	3.5
10. Classify and sort new information.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	9
11. Select or reject a source based on difficulty level, relevance and currency.	0.157	2.67	Not Met	12.5
12. Assess the reliability, objectivity and authenticity of a source.	0.157	2.67	Not Met	12.5
13. Summarise and paraphrase information in one's own words.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	1.5
Overall Average Weighted Mean		2.90	Moderately Met	

Table 5 shows the results of the performance of the learning outcome of the students in their research skills, find specific information using internet search engines and electronic resources and summarise and paraphrase information in one's own words (AWM=3.11) moderately met, list the key ideas to guide search for information and cite a source in accordance with academic conventions (AWM=3.00) moderately met, use the library system for finding, borrowing and returning library material, use an English dictionary for language learning, use a content page and an index to locate information in a book, locate a book/journal in the library using the catalogue, find topic-related information in a book/journal in the library using the catalogue and classify and sort new information (AWM=2.89) moderately met, select or reject a source based on difficulty level, relevance and currency and assess the reliability, objectivity and authenticity of a source (AWM=2.67) not met. The overall (AWM=2.90) moderately met which means that students have little skills in research skills learning outcome among them.

Table 6: Performance of students in their learning outcome in taking notes

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Recall and define main concepts.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	1.5
2. Utilize abbreviations and symbols.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	3
3. Use English rather than Arabic for notes in margins and glossing vocabulary.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	5.5
4. Extract and record key information (the gist) from a written or spoken source based on own interpretation of information.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	5.5
5. Adopt a note-taking strategy (e.g. Cornell system; mind mapping).	0.157	2.67	Not Met	10
6. Support key points with relevant additional details.	0.173	2.78	Not Met	8.5
7. Organise information to enable quick reference at a later date.	0.173	2.78	Not Met	8.5
8. Date one's notes and use notes to create a summary.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	5.5
9. Reproduce key information and supporting details from notes in one's own words.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	1.5
10. Sort out information and reject irrelevant pieces.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	5.5
Overall Average Weighted Mean		2.90	Moderately Met	

Table 6 shows the results of the performance of the students learning outcome in their note taking skills, recall and define main concepts and reproduce key information and supporting details from notes in one's own words (AWM=3.11) moderately met, utilize abbreviations and symbols (AWM=3.00) moderately met, use English rather than Arabic for notes in margins and glossing vocabulary, extract and record key information (the gist) from a written or spoken source based on own interpretation of

information, date one's notes and use notes to create a summary and sort out information and reject irrelevant pieces (AWM=2.89) moderately met, support key points with relevant additional details and organise information to enable quick reference at a later date (AWM=2.78) not met and adopt a note-taking strategy (e.g. Cornell system; mind mapping) (AWM=2.67) not met. The overall (AWM=2.90) moderately met which means that students have limited skills in taking notes learning outcome.

Table 7: Performance of students in their learning outcome in giving presentation

Indicators	SD	AWM	Description	Ranking
1. Outline and define main concepts.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	7.5
2. Address questions from the audience.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	7.5
3. Plan and conduct a presentation based on information from written material, interviews, surveys, etc.	0.248	3.33	Moderately Met	3
4. Speak in a clearly audible and well-paced voice.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	7.5
5. Follow a presentation format.	0.218	3.11	Moderately Met	7.5
6. Use presentation language (discourse markers etc.).	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	10.5
7. Achieve the key aim of informing the audience.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	12.5
8. Make use of audio/visual aids when giving oral presentation.	0.262	3.44	Met	1.5
9. Tailor content and language to the level of the audience.	0.233	3.22	Moderately Met	4.5
10. Maintain some eye contact with audience.	0.189	2.89	Moderately Met	12.5
11. Speak from notes in front of an audience using index cards.	0.204	3.00	Moderately Met	10.5
12. Observe time restriction in presentation.	0.262	3.44	Met	1.5
13. Organise and present information in a logical order at a comprehensible speed.	0.233	3.22	Moderately Met	4.5
14. Invite constructive feedback and self-evaluate the presentation.	0.141	2.56	Not Met	14
Overall Average Weighted Mean		3.10	Moderately Met	

Table 7 shows the results of the performance of the learning outcome of students in giving presentation. Make uses of audio/visual aids when giving oral presentation and observe time restriction in presentation (AWM=3.44) met, plan and conduct a presentation based on information from written material, interviews, surveys, etc. (AWM=3.33) moderately met, tailor content and language to the level of the audience and organise and present information in a logical order at a comprehensible speed

(AWM=4.5) moderately met, outline and define main concepts, address questions from the audience and speak in a clearly audible and well-paced voice and follow a presentation format (AWM=3.11) moderately met, use presentation language (discourse markers etc.) and speak from notes in front of an audience using index cards (AWM=3.00) moderately met, achieve the key aim of informing the audience and maintain some eye contact with audience (AWM=2.89) moderately met and invite constructive feedback and self-evaluate the presentation (AWM=2.56) not met. The overall (AWM=3.10) moderately met which means that students have limited skills in giving presentation learning outcome.

Table 8: Significant relationship between the performance of student in their written report and performance of the student in their learning outcome in the GSS module

Variables	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant *not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
Portfolio			
• Management time & accept responsibility	1.507	not significant	accepted
• Research skills	1.670	not significant	accepted
• Note taking	1.572	not significant	accepted
• Giving presentation	1.349	not significant	accepted
Guided Learning			
• Management time & accept responsibility	1.922	significant	rejected
• Research skills	1.412	not significant	accepted
• Note taking	2.091	significant	rejected
• Giving presentation	1.140	not significant	accepted
Group Oral Presentation			
• Management time & accept responsibility	1.907	significant	rejected
• Research skills	1.401	not significant	accepted
• Note taking	2.072	significant	rejected
• Giving presentation	1.131	not significant	accepted
Significant level at 0.05 level, one tailed test, df at 7 with critical value of 1.895			

Table 8 shows the results of the significant relationship between the performance of the student in their written report and the performance of the students in their learning outcome in the module. It shows that when portfolio is tested against management time and accept responsibility, r value is 1.507, portfolio is tested against research skills, r value is 1.607, portfolio is tested against note taking, r value is 1.572, portfolio is tested against giving presentation, r value is 1.349 in which the relationship is not significant and the hypothesis is accepted. However, when guided learning is tested against management time and accept responsibility, r value is 1.922, guided learning is tested against note taking, r value is 2.091 which mean the relationship is significant and hypothesis is rejected, but when guided learning is tested against research skills, r value

is 1.412, guided learning when tested against giving presentation, r value is 1.140 which mean the relationship is not significant and the hypothesis is accepted. Similarly, when oral group presentation is tested against management time and accept responsibility and note taking the computed r values are 1.907 and 2.072 which mean the relationship is significant and the hypothesis is rejected, while oral group presentation is tested against research skills and giving presentation, r values are 1.403 and 1.131 in which the relationship is not significant and the hypothesis is accepted.

5. Discussion

General Study Skills (GSS) performance of the students' written report in their portfolio is based on the skills needed in the module, however; students need to practice the skills because most of them cannot make it due to limited knowledge they have in the module. The knowledge in their learning skills must be based on their ability to learn. Understanding student learning provides an in-depth analysis of students' learning methods in their module, at a time. It examines the extent to which these learning methods reflect the teaching, assessment and individual personalities of the student involvement. It contains techniques and clearer insight into the process of student learning (Arends & Castle, 2015). On the other hand, portfolio written reports evaluate the quality of the module in their skills. It also determines the academic standard and requirement of the module. It helps students to reflect their ability in their academic goals and progress in their learning process and skills. It provides richer, deeper and more accurate picture of their learning process and it represents performance of the students inside the classroom. Skills development programs are based on different theories of how students learn and how teachers provide learning among their students. The main idea that teachers should learn and a strategy for helping teachers enact that idea within their own ongoing systems of practice. The pedagogies used to facilitate teaching effectiveness give a better output on the written reports of the students in their study skills (Kennedy, 2016).

Moreover, performance of students in their guided learning written reports show moderately met, however; it gives new learning experiences to students because they are given a chance to express and write as part of their skills. It is helped and designed for the students to learn from their classmates by asking insights on the written report they do. This is the best way for the students to learn and do something as part of their skills in their guided learning. They have a chance to experience a wide range of academic freedom as part of their learning process. Guided learning is a chance for them to work in groups, in pairs, in debates, in presentations and in tutorials among them. They can learn from each other. Guided learning also is a supplement for their independent study as based on their experiences and insights in life. This can even improve their skills in carrying out specific task among them. Self-efficacy and student learning outcomes is apparent as value, self-regulation and metacognition, locus of control, intrinsic motivation, and strategy learning use. Student self-efficacy can be

improved using teaching strategies that may be used to improve self-efficacy and learning skills that can be provided for the students (Bartimote et. al., 2016).

Hence, performance of students in their oral group presentation shows that moderately met because students are not exposed to develop skills in their learning skills and need to be developed on them. Develop the potentials of the students in their presentation would mean helping them cultivate their confidence in their presentation. Help students to widen their horizon and skills in exploring their topic through research since learning skills are based on research at present. This is globally known in the world that resulted to competency learning based among the students. Oral group presentation develops the self-esteem of the students and develops their speaking exposure, however; their exposure is moderately met. Student can be able to apply all the principles learnt in the module. However, due to their limited knowledge and lack of exposure, lots of things to be improved and needed for their skills. Other students can follow the procedures and format of the presentation but to others are not. This is the reason why their performance is below par. Oral presentation is the assessment of their performance skills in their module. Performance of students in their oral group presentation provides skills on their learning process in terms of research and in terms of their writing (Schechner, 2017).

Furthermore, performance of students in their learning outcome in management time and accept responsibility shows moderately met. This is based on how they manage their time and accept responsibility. They work in pairs or groups and participate in discussion and express their opinion and insights. They also follow the rules and regulations on attendance and punctuality as part of their learning process and their assessment. They are required to submit projects, assignments and projects on time especially on the activities that have deadlines. They listen and respect to opinion from their classmates and teachers. They create term planners and study schedules particularly for those students who are working and at the same time studying. Independent access is provided for them through internet and in any form of communication and project in their module as a part of their learning activity and responsibility. They have different techniques, strategies in learning depends on their convenience and their study habits and describe learning experiences and challenges during their presentation and written report output. The ability to carry out research successfully has come to be seen as a key transferable skill required of all higher education students and the management of a student research project addresses directly the skill elements. This provides a clear, comprehensive and useful guide to students undertaking research projects in order to improve their chances of a successful outcome (Sharp, Peters & Howard, 2017).

In particular, performance of students in their learning outcome in research skills shows moderately met because they are provided the framework, key ideas and guide to research information. The access of the library, computer is provided for their research project. Facilities are upgraded for the access of the students in their research project. Everything is provided and proper guidance are given with full of emphasis because research is important in their learning process. Students are given enough

knowledge on how to make research. They are driven and obliged to make research as part of their curriculum and as part of their module. Their learning outcome assesses their performance in their research skills. Students are often encouraged to maximize their engagement with supervised research and minimize teaching obligations. However, the process of teaching students engaged in inquiry provides practice in the application of important research skills and contributes substantially to the improvement of essential research skills among the students (Feldon, et. al., 2011).

Whereas, performance of students in their learning outcome in taking notes shows moderately met among them. Students can define main concepts of their module. However, there is a need to push them through to reach their learning outcome. They are poor in writing English because they are exposed to Arabic. Sometime study habits of students affect their learning outcome in terms of note taking. It is hard for them to extract words especially when the words are unfamiliar with them. They have problems on spelling. There is a need to organise their taught to enable them to take note properly. This is a problem for them. They wanted to feed them everything in their module, they cannot reproduce key information and supporting details on their own words. Note taking is a skill for the performance of the students (Chang & Ku, 2015).

In like manner, the performance of the students in their leaning outcome in giving presentation shows moderately met since the module outline is defined with concepts for the students to follow. They address questions of the audience for further clarifications among them. They plan and conduct presentation based on the information needed in the module. The presentation needs further improvement especially on the delivery of their work output. They are not confident and need to develop skills in the delivery of the module. Glad that they follow the format of the presentation in achieving the key aim of the presentation of their group. They are using the slides, audio and visual as part of their presentation. Organise and present information in logical order at a comprehensible speed. They are opened to suggestion and feedback regarding their work output and presentation for the evaluation of their project. The impact of cognitive factors on academic achievement is a motivational and situational factor on the academic achievement of students. This explores the self-concept on academic achievement, and examine whether intrinsic motivation moderates the effect of academic achievement of students. Students should pay more attention to the enhancement of motivational factors (e.g., self-concept and motivation) to improve students' academic achievements (Khalaila, 2015).

6. Conclusions

1. Performance of students in their written report output in terms of portfolio is not met, guided learning is moderately met and group oral presentation is moderately met.

2. Performance of students in their learning output in terms of management time and accept responsibility is moderately met, research skills is moderately met, note taking is moderately met and giving oral presentation is moderately met.

6.1 Recommendations

1. Written reports in the module should be designed properly based on the knowledge of the students be it in the portfolio, guided learning and their oral group presentation. Most of them have a hard time in producing good output written report.
2. There is a need to revise the module in the General Study Skills because most of the learning outcome is not met. Design module programs that suit the needs of the students based on their ability and capacity. Basic learning outcome must be imposed to get a good learning outcome among the students.

References

- Arends, R., & Castle, S. (2015). *Learning to teach* (Vol. 2). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Bartimote-Aufflick, K., Bridgeman, A., Walker, R., Sharma, M., & Smith, L. (2016). The study, evaluation, and improvement of university student self-efficacy. *Studies in Higher Education*, 41(11), 1918-1942.
- Chang, W. C., & Ku, Y. M. (2015). The effects of note-taking skills instruction on elementary students' reading. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(4), 278-291.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- Feldon, D. F., Peugh, J., Timmerman, B. E., Maher, M. A., Hurst, M., Strickland, D., ... & Stiegelmeier, C. (2011). Graduate students' teaching experiences improve their methodological research skills. *Science*, 333(6045), 1037-1039.
- Gillies, A. (2017). *Note-taking for consecutive interpreting: a short course*. Routledge.
- Griffin, P., & Care, E. (Eds.). (2014). *Assessment and teaching of 21st century skills: Methods and approach*. Springer.
- Feldon, D. F., Peugh, J., Timmerman, B. E., Maher, M. A., Hurst, M., Strickland, D., ... & Stiegelmeier, C. (2011). Graduate students' teaching experiences improve their methodological research skills. *Science*, 333(6045), 1037-1039.
- Haßler, B., Major, L., & Hennessy, S. (2016). Tablet use in schools: A critical review of the evidence for learning outcomes. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 32(2), 139-156.
- Jackson, S. L. (2014). *Research methods: A modular approach*. Cengage Learning.
- Khalaila, R. (2015). The relationship between academic self-concept, intrinsic motivation, test anxiety, and academic achievement among nursing students: Mediating and moderating effects. *Nurse Education Today*, 35(3), 432-438.

- Kennedy, M. M. (2016). How does professional development improve teaching?. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 945-980.
- Kerzner, H., & Kerzner, H. R. (2017). *Project management: a systems approach to planning, scheduling, and controlling*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Schechner, R. (2017). *Performance studies: An introduction*. Routledge.
- Sharp, J. A., Peters, J., & Howard, K. (2017). *The management of a student research project*. Routledge.
- Van Emden, J., & Becker, L. (2016). *Presentation skills for students*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- York, T. T., Gibson, C., & Rankin, S. (2015). *Defining and Measuring Academic Success. Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 20.

Leovigildo Lito D. Mallillin
ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL STUDY SKILLS PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS
IN THE CENTRE OF FOUNDATION STUDIES

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).